

Application of Machine Learning to Predict the Impact of Trace Element Addition on Biomethane Potential of Dairy Industry Wastewater

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Abstract

This research aimed to investigate the impact of trace elements on biomethane potential within the context of dairy industry wastewater treatment, utilizing machine learning (ML) to optimize biogas production. Wastewater from the dairy industry contains various trace elements, such as nickel, cobalt, and iron, which are crucial for optimizing anaerobic digestion processes. However, fluctuating concentrations and intricate chemical interactions within wastewater pose challenges to their quantification and effective optimization of biogas outputs. By employing ML models, this study identified the most impactful trace elements and developed predictive models for biomethane production. The findings are expected to offer significant insights into enhancing renewable energy generation from dairy industry wastewater, contributing to sustainable waste management and energy practices.

Keywords: Biomethane, Trace Elements, Artificial Intelligence, Dairy Industry Wastewater, Anaerobic Digestion, Machine Learning.

INTRODUCTION

Methane yield can be limited in certain cases due to various factors, including the deficiency of trace elements, which play a crucial role in microbial metabolism. This issue is particularly relevant in the anaerobic treatment of dairy industry wastewater, where nutrient imbalances may hinder efficient biogas production. The presence of specific trace elements can enhance the anaerobic digestion of dairy industry wastewater, leading to increased methane yields (Wang et al., 2019). However, the specific concentration of each element is critical, as adding excessive amounts of metals can lead to toxicity and inhibit microbial activity (Zhang et al., 2020). Thus, understanding the optimal levels of trace elements for maximizing methane yields remains a focus of ongoing research in the context of dairy industry wastewater.

The integration of machine learning (ML) into anaerobic digestion processes, particularly in optimizing trace element concentrations for biomethane production from dairy industry wastewater, has shown promising results. ML techniques are capable of handling extensive datasets, thereby enabling precise predictions and adjustments in the anaerobic process (Wang et al., 2023). The integration of ML in anaerobic treatment has therefore a potential for a deeper understanding of the factors influencing BMP, paving the way for more efficient and sustainable wastewater treatment systems. Various ML techniques have been applied to optimize the anaerobic digestion process (Almomani et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023; Zhan and Zhu, 2024). Nevertheless, research investigating the application of various machine learning methods, including tree-based algorithms, in this context remains limited.

The major aim of the present study was to analyze the impact of trace element concentration on the anaerobic digestion of the dairy industry wastewater and utilize tree-based ML algorithms to build predictive models for methane yield optimization. The outcomes of this study are crucial as they are expected to provide valuable insights into the role of trace elements in anaerobic digestion, and offer data-driven predictive models to improve methane yield, contributing to more efficient and sustainable wastewater treatment processes in the dairy industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, dairy industry wastewater was taken from an influent line of a full-scale dairy industry wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) with a production capacity of 1000 tons/day. It produces various products such as milk, yogurt, ayran, cheese, butter, cream, salep, and kefir. The chemical oxygen demand (COD) concentration was measured as 3860 ± 45 mg/L, with a soluble COD (sCOD) to COD ratio of 57 ± 1 % in dairy industry wastewater. The BMP tests were conducted under mesophilic conditions at a temperature of 35 °C via the Automatic Methane Potential Test Systems II from Bioprocess Control (AMPTS II, Sweden). The BMP test was performed in triplicate, with a mixture ratio of 2:1 between inoculum and substrate on a volatile solid (VS) basis. The working volume of the mixture of inoculum and substrate was 400 mL. In the study, three distinct concentration levels were selected for each trace element to assess their impacts on methane production. Cobalt (Co) concentrations were set at 0.1, 0.2, and 0.4 mg/L, Ferrous (Fe) at 1, 5, and 10 mg/L, and Nickel (Ni) at 0.1, 0.2, and 0.4 mg/L. The COD, sCOD, TS, VS, TN, NH₄-N, and TP were measured based on Standard Methods (APHA, 2017).

In this study, one of the widely utilized tree-based ML algorithms, namely the Gradient Boosting, was employed

to build predictive models for methane yield optimization. In this study, the Gradient Boosting Machine was developed using the results obtained from the experiments. To validate the generalization ability of the model, the data were divided into two groups, i.e., training and testing sets. While data pertaining to 10 different scenarios was used to train the model, the remaining 5 scenario were utilized for testing. In the developed model, Co, Ni, and Fe were selected as independent variables, whereas the BMP was chosen as the target variable. The model's hyperparameters were optimized using the grid search algorithm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Experimental Results

The BMP results demonstrated that supplementing trace elements significantly enhances the methane yield of dairy industry wastewater. S7 exhibited the highest BMP value of 362 ± 10 mL CH₄/g VS, demonstrating the positive effect of the addition of Fe at 10 mg/L combined with other elements. In addition, Wang et al. (2019) highlighted the role of Co and Ni in supporting enzymatic functions essential for methanogenesis. The lowest BMP value was observed for S11, with a value of 147 ± 19 mL CH₄/g VS. This finding might be related to elevated Ni concentrations that may inhibit methane production.

Tree-based Machine Learning Results

As mentioned above, one of the efficient tree-based ML algorithms, namely the Gradient Boosting, was utilized for performing the BMP predictions. The performance of the constructed model was assessed using the commonly used coefficient of determination (R^2) and the results were visually represented by the scatter plots as depicted in Figure 1. Following validation, it was determined that the input combination yielding the optimal BMP value—based on simulations conducted within the range and precision of the independent inputs provided in Table 1—was 0.18 mg/L Co, 0.21 mg/L Ni, and 8.58 mg/L Fe, resulting in a BMP value of 351.07 mL CH₄/g VS. This approach enabled the prediction of the optimal BMP value at a statistically significant level with a minimal number of experiments.

Figure 1. Scatter plot of train and test set.

Table 1. Search range and resolution.

Inputs	Range (mg/L)	Resolution (mg/L)
Co	[0-0.5]	0.01
Ni	[0-0.5]	0.01
Fe	[1-10]	0.01

CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to elucidate the influence of trace element addition on biomethane production in the anaerobic treatment of dairy industry wastewater while using the Gradient Boosting Machine to develop predictive tools for improving methane yield. Tree-based machine learning results revealed that the combination of 0.18 mg/L Co, 0.21 mg/L Ni, and 8.58 mg/L Fe provided the BMP value of 351.07 mL CH₄/g VS. The outcomes of this study are of critical importance, as they provide invaluable insights into the role of trace elements in anaerobic digestion. Moreover, the study offers data-driven predictive models to optimize methane yield, thereby contributing to more efficient and sustainable wastewater treatment processes in the dairy industry.

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